

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding methods

Agronomic performance and genetic correlations of rice mutants

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By using different mutagen doses, we isolated five mutants in rice varieties IR8, Jhona, and Basmati (Table 1). Both mutants of IR8 (IRm₁ and IRm₆) are early and fine-grained, with higher seed protein content. Both mutants of Jhona (Jm₁ and Jm₄) are shorter and yield higher than their parent. Jm₄ has higher grain number and grain yield than Jm₁. Basmati mutant Bm₁ has shorter duration and is shorter and has finer grains, with higher grain number, protein content, and seed yield, than Basmati.

Although the genetic parameters phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation, heritability, genetic advance, and expected genetic advance were not different in the mutants, significant differences in certain genetic correlations were exhibited (Table 2). Grain yield became negatively correlated with grain fineness and positively correlated with grain weight; these correlations are not significant in the parent varieties. Grain fineness in the parent varieties is not correlated with grain weight and grain

Table 1. Performance of rice mutants and their parent lines. Kurukshetra University, India.

Parent and mutant	Mutagen and dosage ^a	Shoot height ^a (cm)	Maturity ^a (d)	Fertile grain ^a (no.)	Grain fineness ^a	Grain yield ^a (g/plant)	Seed protein content ^b (%)
IR8	—	88.1	153	753	2.39	21.1	7.6
IRm ₁	EMS 1.5%	110.5	128	903	2.84	22.7	8.2
IRm ₆	EMS 1.5%	88.7	119	982	2.66	22.5	8.7
	LSD (0.05)	3.9	5.7	19.9	0.13	1.2	0.2
Jhona	—	133.5	127	1012	2.29	20.4	7.8
Jm ₁	EMS 1.5%	122.9	125	1081	2.45	22.9	7.9
Jm ₄	r-rays 20 kR + 1% EMS	124.5	123	1130	2.47	24.1	7.7
	LSD (0.05)	5.8	7.4	28.31	0.09	1.6	0.15
Basmati	—	151.8	152	789	3.63	15.9	7.6
Bm ₁	EMS 0.5%	140.7	142	878	3.60	17.4	8.4
	LSD (0.05)	5.2	4.5	21.6	0.08	0.1	0.1

^aMean of 360 observations (40 plants × 3 replications × 3 generations). ^bMean of 90 observations (10 plants × 3 replications × 3 generations).

Table 2. Correlations^a of genetic traits between parent varieties and mutant lines. Kurukshetra University, India.

Trait		GY	GF	GW	GN	SH
Grain yield (GY)	Parent	ns	ns	ns	+	ns
	Mutant	ns	—	+	+	ns
Grain fineness (GF)	Parent	.05	ns	ns	ns	+
	Mutant	-.29*	ns	—	—	+
Grain weight (GW)	Parent	.15	-.49	ns	—	ns
	Mutant	.29*	-.25*	ns	—	—
Grain number (GN)	Parent	.70*	.39	-.59*	ns	ns
	Mutant	.22*	-.14*	-.23*	ns	ns
Shoot height (SH)	Parent	-.02	.39*	-.15	.09	ns
	Mutant	.23	.31*	-.28*	.21	ns

^ans = not significant, + = positive, - = negative, * = significant value, SE > \bar{n} .

number; in the mutants, these correlations are negative and significant. Shoot height in the mutants is negatively correlated with grain weight; in the parents, this correlation is not

significant.

Whether these represent mutational changes or chance changes needs to be determined, using a large sample of mutant types. □

Hybrid rice heterosis in Tamil Nadu

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We studied 38 F₁s involving Zhen Shan 97A and Er-jiu-Nan 1A as the female

parents during 1985 dry season. All combinations had high standard heterosis and heterobeltiosis for tiller numbers (see table).

High tiller numbers were reflected in straw yield, with standard heterosis as high as 134% and heterobeltiosis as high as 112%. Standard heterosis for grain yield was only 8%, because of heterosis

for spikelet sterility as high as 226% compared to the standard variety and 909% compared to the pollen parents.

Heterosis for tiller number gives scope for improving hybrid seed fertility by selecting restorers for genetic constitution and CMS lines for cytoplasmic content. □

Heterosis^a in 38 combinations. Coimbatore, India, 1985 dry season.

Character studied ^b	26 combinations (ovule parent used: Zhen Shan 97A)				12 combinations (ovule parent used: Er-jiu-Nan 1A)			
	Range of standard heterosis (%)		Range of heterobeltiosis (%)		Range of standard heterosis (%)		Range of heterobeltiosis (%)	
	From	To	From	To	From	To	From	To
Plant ht (cm)	-42.53 (Kanchi)	-2.12 (K. Samba)	-49.72 (PTB10)	+17.81 (TNAU658)	-34.09 (IET5103)	11.12 (IR9698)	-41.32 (IET6208)	+7.12 (IR19053)
Tiller number per plant	+100.00 (IET1722)	+242.85 (TNAU4372)	+111.11 (Co 13)	+242.85 (TNAU4372)	+117.14 (IET3267)	+222.85 (IR2307)	+111.11 (IET3267)	+207.93 (IR9715)
Panicle length (cm)	-19.46 (Co 33)	+0.44 (ASD8)	-24.80 (BAS370)	+25.41 (ASD8)	-19.02 (IR9698)	-2.21 (IR19053)	-18.30 (IR9698)	+11.61 (IR19053)
Spikelets per panicle	-65.85 (TNAU658)	-9.15 (Co 37)	-54.10 (TNAU658)	+41.84 (IR50)	-48.17 (IR9698)	-12.80 (AS19789)	-67.81 (IET6208)	+53.32 (IR2307)
Grain yield per plant (g)	-81.77 (BAS370)	-8.33 (AD9246)	-87.27 (BAS370)	-3.82 (AD9246)	-65.26 (IR19053)	+7.89 (IET6208)	-69.01 (IET5103)	+11.11 (IR9698)
Grain number per panicle	-93.6 (ADT31)	-74.4 (K. Samba)	-93.10 (ADT31)	-43.01 (IR36)	-94.16 (IR2307)	-47.76 (IET6208)	-87.14 (IR2307)	-36.19 (IR19053)
Unfilled grains per panicle	-5.12 (TNAU658)	+238.46 (Co 37)	+77.94 (TNAU4372)	+728.57 (PY2)	-46.93 (IET5103)	+226.02 (IET3630)	+7.21 (IET5103)	+908.94 (IR2307)
Straw wt (g)	-42.50 (IR9752)	+91.25 (IR56)	-47.50 (TNAU4372)	+90.62 (Co 37)	-30.00 (IR19053)	+134.37 (IET6208)	-11.66 (IR18599)	+111.65 (BPHR5)

^aStandard heterosis compared with Co 37, heterobeltiosis compared with pollen parent. Variety in brackets = pollen parent. ^bAv for 5 plants.

Variation in stigma exertion in rice

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Stigma exertion rate (SER) in 105 cultivars from Zhejiang and Taiwan, China, and from India was examined in late 1983 and 21 floral and panicle characteristics including stigma exertion were examined in 330 cultivars from Taihu Valley and Yunnan Province in late 1984. Variation in SER in relation to other agronomic and morphological traits was examined by correlation, path, cluster, and principal component analyses.

SER ranged from 0 to 76% (mean 12.8%) among the cultivars observed in 1983 (see table). SER was 0-76% (mean 19.9%), in indica rices and 0-40% (mean 5.9%) in japonicas. SER ranged from 0 to 69% (mean 8.5%) among the cultivars observed in 1984. The mean SER in indicas (19.3%) was higher than that in

Variation in SER in cultivars. Hangzhou, China, 1983-84.

Cultivars		SER (%)					
Type	No.	Mean	Upland rice		Lowland rice		
			Mean	Range	Mean	Range	
Observed in 1983	105	12.8	18.8	0 -54.3	11.2	0-75.9	
Indicas	52	19.9	21.1	2.3-34.8	19.4	0-75.9	
Japonicas	53	5.9	14.7	0 -54.3	2.3	0-39.7	
Observed in 1984 ^a	330	8.5	30.5	5.6-54.2	5.3	0-68.6	
Indicas	19	19.3	30.7	10.5-52.6	16.3	0-63.2	
Japonicas	306	7.6	30.5	5.6-54.2	5.6	0-68.6	
From Yunnan	84	23.2	30.5	5.6-54.2	20.7	0-68.6	
Indicas	18	16.9	30.7	10.5-52.6	12.9	0-46.3	
Japonicas	61	25.2	30.5	5.6-54.2	22.9	0-68.6	

^aSome cultivars from Yunnan were medium type in indica-japonica differentiation.

japonicas from Taihu Valley (3.2%), but lower than that in japonicas from Yunnan plateau (25.2%). Upland rices showed higher SER (18.8% in 1983 and 30.5% in 1984) than lowland rices (11.2% in 1983 and 5.3% in 1984).

Cultivars from Yunnan could be divided into two groups on the basis of differences in SER, which were in proportion to numbers of lowland and upland rices. Differences between cultivars from Yunnan and Taihu Valley

on the scatter diagram were in concordance with differences in SER (see figure).

Major characteristics contributing to SER were classified as stigma characteristics (outwardly curved stigma, pistil length, number of stigma branches), spikelet characteristics (length, width, and length:width ratio), and angle of floret opening. Glume pubescence and awn length also may be used as indirect indices of SER. □